

CHILDREN'S CREATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN TECHNOLOGY LESSONS

P. S. Djurayeva

Pedagogical skill center of Navoiy region, "Preschool, primary and special educational methods"
department associate docent

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15683347>

Abstract. *This article examines methods and strategies for developing students' creative thinking skills in technology lessons. It highlights the importance of introducing innovative approaches, problem-solving exercises, and hands-on projects to enhance students' creativity. Additionally, the role of technology in critical thinking and independent learning is explored. The research findings show that creative thinking skills can be effectively developed through interactive and student-centered learning environments.*

Keywords: *thinking skills, creative thinking, information literacy, technology lessons, job market, multifunctional solutions.*

Introduction

Developing students' creative thinking skills is one of the most important tasks in the modern education system. The subject of technology is one of the main areas that allows students to improve their creative abilities and implement innovative ideas. However, in many schools, teaching is based on traditional methods and innovative approaches that develop creative thinking are insufficiently used. In today's rapidly changing world, students must not only learn to absorb ready-made information, but also learn to analyze it independently and find new solutions. Technology classes provide a good opportunity to achieve this goal, as they allow students to combine theory with practice and learn to implement their ideas. However, many educational programs prioritize standard tasks and do not provide sufficient opportunities for students to think independently and engage in creative inquiry. To develop creative thinking, it is necessary to update teaching methods and widely use interactive and project-based learning approaches. By organizing tasks and projects in technology classes that are interesting and develop students' imagination, you can increase their creative abilities. This study examines ways to develop students' creative thinking through the subject of technology and suggests effective methods.

Importance of the topic: Developing students' creative thinking skills is one of the most important and relevant issues in the modern education system. Today, the rapid development of technology and the constant change of society impose new requirements on the education system. Specialists in demand in the labor market are those who can think creatively, make non-standard decisions, and propose innovative ideas.

Research materials and methodology.

The goals and objectives of the project work are: The main objectives of the study are to identify effective methods and approaches aimed at developing students' creative thinking skills in technology lessons, to study the theoretical foundations of developing students' creative thinking skills, to analyze modern teaching methods and strategies that can be used in technology lessons, to develop practical tasks and projects that will help students improve their creative thinking skills, and to provide recommendations aimed at developing creative thinking in technology lessons.

Plan 1: Identify the problem

Nowadays, students' creative thinking skills have declined, and they are increasingly relying on ready-made solutions. Technology classes often focus on standard tasks, while students' skills to independently come up with ideas and implement them are not fully developed. Today, creative thinking is needed not only in the fields of art and literature, but in all disciplines, especially in technological disciplines. The development of students' creative thinking in technology classes is achieved through their participation in project work, the presentation of innovative ideas, solving complex problems and finding solutions. This process contributes to the formation of students' abilities to be inventive, innovative and provide multifunctional solutions.

The goal of the project:

- to increase the creative abilities of students in technology lessons.
- to develop creative thinking skills through practical tasks.
- to create conditions for students to make independent decisions and implement new ideas.

The objectives of the project:

- to identify effective methods for developing creative thinking.
- to increase the activity of students by giving them creative tasks.
- to use design thinking and the project method.
- to show the importance of the projects created by students in life.

Problems:

1. Insufficient development of creative thinking. Students rely only on standard solutions, limiting creativity. In technology classes, only ready-made solutions and methods are used, and new ideas and independent work skills are not developed. This leads to limiting creativity.

2. Lack of tools and equipment: The insufficient use of new technologies and tools in schools, the lack of opportunities for students to work with modern solutions and techniques, hinder the development of creative thinking.

3. Often repetitive tasks: Students are given repetitive tasks, so they do not have enough time to come up with new ideas and innovative solutions. To encourage students to work creatively, tasks should be varied and open-ended, meaning they should be given the opportunity to express themselves.

Search results. 2- plan: Project-based learning method

1. Through project-based learning, students work on the topic "Yurts - an engineering solution for nomadic people." This method consists of the following stages:

- Problem definition:
 - Study the modern significance of the yurt (ecological houses, mobile shelters).
 - Search for ways to integrate the yurt structure with modern technologies.

- Planning:

Study the main parts of a yurt (kerege, uyk, shanyrak, door).

- Select the necessary materials to create a small model of a yurt.
- Implementation:
 - Create a model from environmentally friendly materials (wood, felt, recycled materials).
 - Decorate the yurt and add design elements.
- Protection and evaluation:
 - Present the project, show its features and areas of application.

Through this method, students develop not only their creative abilities, but also their structural thinking, engineering skills, and knowledge of national culture.

2. Design Thinking Method

The Design Thinking method allows students to look at the yurt from a new perspective. This method consists of the following steps:

1. Identify the problem – What changes can be made to create a modern yurt?
2. Suggest ideas – Consider ecological, modern, functional versions of the yurt.
3. Sketch – Draw a model of the yurt on paper or in a computer program.
4. Product Design – Build a small model of a yurt and demonstrate its features.
5. Defense and Feedback – Present the finished project and prove its importance.

Through this method, students develop creative thinking, engineering design, and visual design skills.

3STEAM method (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, Mathematics)

The project "Yurt - a combination of tradition and science" is implemented using the STEAM method:

- Science: Study of the environmental benefits of the yurt, the properties of natural materials.

- Technology: Using 3D printing or computer programs to model the construction of a yurt.

- Engineering: Studying the structural strength of a yurt, calculating its resistance to wind and rain.

- Art: Show the artistic uniqueness of the yurt through national ornaments and decorative elements.

- Mathematics: Calculate the dimensions of the yurt, analyze geometric shapes.

This method allows students to connect scientific and technical skills with national values.

4. Practical tasks and game methods

Practical tasks and game elements are used to develop students' creative abilities:

- "Building a yurt" - Build a small model of a yurt and correctly arrange its parts.

- "Modern Yurt" project - Invent a modern version of the yurt (for example, energy-efficient, collapsible yurts).

- "Engineering Competition" - Organize a competition among students to make the structure of the yurt as strong as possible.

These tasks develop students' logical thinking, creativity, and engineering skills.

Plan 3: Project Implementation

In this section, we will look at the creative and practical stages of implementing a yurt project. During the project, students will create their own models, combining tradition and modern technology.

1. Preliminary Preparation and Research

- Cultural and Historical Background:

Students will first study the historical development of the yurt and its national culture. During this stage, the meaning of the yurt, its structural features, and its ecological benefits will be analyzed.

Objective: To gain a deeper understanding of the national heritage and to form the ideological basis of the project.

- Materials and Modern Technologies:

The materials used to create the yurt model (felt, wood, recycled elements) and modern technologies (e.g. LED lighting, energy-saving systems) will be identified.

Objective: To combine traditional elements with innovative methods.

2. Modeling and Innovation Steps. - Group Work and Planning:

Students are divided into groups and create their own project plan. Each group determines how the main parts of a yurt - kerege, uyk, shanyrak, door - will be implemented and introduce their creative ideas.

- Practical Work:

- Modeling of Structural Elements: Constructs the main parts of the yurt as a realistic model.

- Combining Tradition and Innovation: Complements traditional structures with modern technological solutions (for example, energy-saving lighting systems or the use of environmentally friendly materials).

- Aesthetic and Functional Solutions: Makes the model both artistic and functional by introducing national ornaments and decorative elements.

3. Presentation, Analysis and Conclusion

- Interactive Presentation:

Each group presents their finished model in front of the class or at the school project exhibition. During the presentation, students:

- Explains the historical significance and structural features of the yurt;

- Describes the materials used and innovations introduced;

- Demonstrates the environmental and cultural values of the project.

- Discussion and Feedback:

After the presentation, students and teachers will discuss the project's achievements and areas for improvement together.

Objective: To receive feedback on their work and identify ways to improve future projects. Students summarize their experiences during the project, the challenges they encountered, and the results they gained from the creative process. This summary helps them objectively evaluate their work and prepare for future projects.

Discussions. Plan 4: Recommendations and development paths

This section discusses ways to further improve the results obtained within the project, develop students' creative abilities, and make technology lessons even more interesting and effective.

1. Directions for improving the yurt project

- Adding interactive elements. Adapting the yurt layout to modern requirements by adding innovative elements such as LED lighting systems, solar panels, and smart ventilation systems.

- Expanding the material. Using natural materials such as felt, wood, and fabric, as well as 3D printed parts and eco-friendly plastics.

- Creating large-scale projects. In addition to small models, create large-scale models of yurts and display them in the schoolyard or at exhibitions.

2. Expanding the project and connecting it with other subjects

- Mathematics: Calculating the geometric structure of a yurt, determining its volume, area, and proportions.

- Physics: Studying the strength of a yurt, calculating its wind resistance, determining the thermal insulation properties of materials.

- Art: Drawing ornaments on a yurt, developing design elements, and improving finishing work.

- Ecology: Studying the impact of a yurt on nature, using environmentally friendly materials.

3. Developing a yurt project outside of school

- Organizing a creative exhibition. Presenting yurt models created by students at a school exhibition or city/regional competitions.

- Meeting with local craftsmen. Inviting craftsmen involved in yurt making and holding master classes.

- Creating a tourism project. Students can create a modern yurt model for tourists and suggest ways to use it in tourist destinations.

4. Suggestions for the future

- Incorporating creative projects into the school curriculum. Incorporating national and innovative projects such as yurts into the regular school curriculum.

- Developing STEAM. Improving the yurt project in the direction of science, technology, engineering, art and mathematics (STEAM).

- Providing startup ideas to students. Providing students with the opportunity to propose small startup projects to create modern, environmentally friendly, innovative yurts.

These suggestions will allow the yurt project to be improved, expanded, and implemented at a higher level, not just within the school. Students will be able to create projects that can be used in real life, developing their creative, engineering, and environmental thinking skills. Through this project, students develop critical and creative thinking skills, allowing them to present, analyze, and improve their ideas. While creating a yurt model, students learn important skills such as problem identification, solution search, analysis, and the use of innovative methods.

Critical thinking:

- Students will study the structure of a traditional yurt, identifying its advantages and disadvantages.

- They will think logically and critically in every decision-making process, and will try to use the most effective and sustainable materials.

- They will develop the ability to express a reasoned opinion, present arguments, and defend their point of view when defending their projects.

At the end of the project, students will not only learn about traditional culture, but also be able to combine it with modern technologies and take their creativity to a new level. This experience can serve as a basis for their future work in engineering, design, or entrepreneurship. That is, the yurt project is a comprehensive platform that develops students' creative, engineering, environmental, and critical thinking skills.

Conclusion and recommendations

This section discusses the project implementation results, evaluation criteria, and conclusions. Through the project "Yurt - a combination of tradition and modern technology", students are focused on studying national heritage, implementing engineering solutions and modern technologies, and developing creative thinking skills. Results:

- Development of Creativity and Engineering Skills: Students will improve their craft, design, and engineering skills while creating a yurt model.

- Interest in National Culture: The project will promote understanding of national heritage, the essence of traditional structures, and their integration with modern technologies.

- Environmental Responsibility: By using environmentally friendly and recyclable materials, students will develop an attitude towards environmental protection.

- Teamwork and Presentation Skills: During the project, teamwork skills and the ability to express their thoughts accurately and clearly will be developed.

Conclusion: As a result of the project, students will create a functional and aesthetic model of a yurt, combining national traditions and modern technologies. They will:

- Combine Theory and Practice: Investigates the historical significance, structural features, and environmental benefits of the yurt and translates them into a tangible product.

- Adopts Innovative Solutions: Implements new ideas by complementing traditional design with modern technologies.

- Strengthens Personal and Team Development: They will defend their ideas, improve their teamwork and presentation skills. In short, this project will make a significant contribution to the development of students' creative, engineering and aesthetic abilities. It will also lay the foundation for future creative projects by deepening their understanding of national culture and incorporating it into modern solutions.

Developing students' creative thinking skills is one of the most important tasks in the modern education system. The results of the study show that technology classes are one of the subjects that create favorable conditions for improving students' creative abilities. In these classes, students combine theoretical knowledge with practice and acquire skills to implement new ideas. However, traditional teaching methods do not sufficiently contribute to the development of creative thinking. In this regard, there is a need to widely use innovative approaches in technology lessons. Recommendations:

1. Modernize teaching methods - interactive, project-based, and problem-based teaching methods should be widely introduced to develop creative thinking.

2. Use of practical tasks and projects – it is recommended to develop tasks based on real-life situations to increase students' interest and develop their creative abilities.

3. Allowing students to make their own decisions - to develop creative abilities, it is necessary to create conditions for students to conduct their own research, propose innovative solutions, and experiment.

4. Use of modern technologies - the use of digital tools and modern software in the classroom contributes to increasing the creative potential of students.

5. Teacher training - it is important for teachers to master modern teaching methods and use approaches aimed at developing creative thinking.

In general, developing students' creative thinking skills in technology classes allows them to improve their personal abilities, find new solutions, and implement innovative ideas. In this regard, the widespread use of creative teaching methods in the educational process is a modern requirement. In short, this project will make a significant contribution to the development of students' creative, engineering, and aesthetic abilities. It will also lay the foundation for future creative projects by deepening their understanding of national culture and incorporating it into modern solutions.

REFERENCES

1. Niyazmetova N.B., "Technology of developing students' creative qualities in technology classes". A Versatile Teacher, ISSN: 2309-6009, 2020, Issue 2(8).

2. Rustamova M.M., "Multimedia to develop children's creative thinking". Tashkent State Pedagogical University, 2023.
3. Abrosimova E.V., "Development of creative abilities of students in technology classes (from work experience)". Yosh Olim, 2017, issue 36
4. ziyonet.uz
5. stud.kz